

Prospective Study of Early Avascular Necrosis Treated with Core Decompression and Platelet Rich Plasma InfiltrationS.Kishore Babu¹, Kranthi Kiran Sanapala², Kinthala Kishor³¹Associate Professor, Government Medical College, Srikakulam²Senior Resident, Government Medical College, Srikakulam³Senior Resident, GEMS Hospital, Srikakulam

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Kranthi Kiran Sanapala

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Avascular necrosis of the femoral head is a disorder that can lead to the collapse of the femoral head and can progress to secondary osteoarthritis, which would ultimately require a total hip replacement. It can be avoided if the disease is diagnosed at an early stage. Various modalities of treatment available for AVN, conservative modalities like observation and non-weight-bearing, pharmacotherapy like Bisphosphonates, Enoxaparin were found to be effective, Hyperbaric oxygen therapy and Surgical modalities like femoral head preserving procedures (core decompression with or without additional procedure, i.e. synthetic bone grafting, biologic adjuvants – Platelet Rich Plasma, Mesenchymal Stem cells, BMAC etc. and rotational osteotomies) and replacement surgeries.

Objective: This study was done to know the clinical outcomes of treating early stages of AVN with Core decompression and PRP infiltration

Materials and Methods: This study was done at tertiary care teaching hospital in the Department of Orthopaedics at Great Eastern Medical School, Srikakulam, and Andhra Pradesh, India from January 2022 to November 2023. 20 patients were included as per the eligibility criteria. Harris Hip Score was assessed.

Results: Most of the patients were males aged 31-40 years; Alcohol being the most common causative factor. 61.5% cases were classified under type IIA according to Ficat & Arlet staging. Clinical outcome is excellent and good in 65% of cases. The mean pre-operative Harris Hip Score of our study was 67.4, and the mean post-operative Harris hip score of our study was 86.8. Out of 20 cases, 8 patients (30%) showed limitation of the progression of the disease, 5 (15%) patients progressed to the further stages of the disease and 7 patients (55%) had remission of the disease.

Conclusion: This study concludes that Core decompression along with PRP infiltration is safe can be used as a good alternative for or in addition with traditionally performed core decompression and bone grafting. Good preliminary results were obtained in patients with early stages of the disease.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Avascular necrosis (AVN) of the femoral head occurs due to disruption of blood supply to the proximal femur. It is caused by either traumatic or atraumatic etiologies.

The majority of the blood supply to the head of the femur comes from the medial and lateral circumflex branches of the profunda femoris, which itself is a branch of femoral artery. Many different etiologies can precipitate this condition. One of the most traumatic causes is femoral neck fracture or femoral head dislocation from acetabulum. When these type of trauma occur, the blood supply to head of femur can be easily disrupted leading to avascular necrosis. Osteonecrosis is the result in 15%-50% of fractures of the neck of the femur and 10%-25% of

hip dislocations. [1] Chronic steroid use and excessive alcohol consumption represent the bulk of non-traumatic etiologies, contributing to more than 80% of them. Steroid associated osteonecrosis represents the second most common cause of osteonecrosis overall after trauma. Sickle cell disease can often precipitate osteonecrosis. Autoimmune and chronic inflammatory disorders like SLE have association. Vascular diseases secondary to diabetes have been implicated in development of femoral head osteonecrosis. [2]

1. In the early stages of AVN (Ficat & Arlet stage I-IIb), preserving the integrity of the femoral head and preventing its collapse are crucial therapeutic goals. [3]

2. Core decompression, a widely employed intervention, involves drilling into the necrotic area to reduce intra-osseous pressure and enhance blood supply, thereby potentially halting disease progression. However, despite its widespread use, there exists a subset of patients who experience suboptimal outcomes, indicating that alternative or adjunctive therapies might be required. Systematic reviews verified the significantly better head survival rates compared to non-operative treatment options.

Core decompression is one of the usual techniques to preserve the joint, chiefly in pre-collapse phases, but its usefulness is still debated, because this procedure alone does give satisfactory osteogenic activity in the necrotic region. The improvement of regenerative medicine in recent years has gone further than this limit, where core decompression was augmented with added measures like an osteoinductive agent that can boost bone repair.

Platelet-rich-plasma (PRP), which is a fraction take out by the centrifugation of whole blood, plays a vital role in tissue repair, regeneration, and differentiation. It contains various growth factors and also positive effects on the encouragement of bones, blood vessels, and the creation of chondrocytes. [4,5]

Plain X-rays, although not particularly distinguishing early- stages osteonecrosis, are, in general, the first imaging modality used, and they should be ordered in AP and frog-leg lateral views

MRI is the usual imaging investigation for the pre-collapse phases of AVN. An initial osteonecrotic lesion appears as a single-density line on the T1 pictures, characteristically in the anterosuperior region of the femoral head, while T2 I in mages the picture of a double line sign notice. The other hip also must be studied because of 3/4 of the cases existing bilaterally

Objectives: Objectives were to assess the change in Harris Hip Score (HHS) following core decompression with PRP in cases of avascular necrosis of the femoral head.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This is a prospective study to assess the outcomes of core decompression with PRP for avascular necrosis of the femoral head. Patient follow-up was conducted at 12 months postoperatively

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

- Age of patients; 20-50 years
- Ficat and Arlet stage I, IIA and IIB

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with blood dyscrasias
- Patients who received chemotherapy and medications that decrease bone marrow function, and platelet count <175,000/ μ L
- Sepsis, septic arthritis, osteomyelitis, or other ongoing infectious processes;

Sample Size: 20 patients of AVN meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria, between the duration of January 2022 to November 2023 were selected from the orthopaedics outpatient department of Great eastern medical School and Hospital, Srikakulam .Consent was taken from all the patients before the start of this study. Detailed histories like personal history (Alcohol consumption) and treatment history (Steroids) was taken from patients and their attendants. Comprehensive systemic and local examinations were conducted. Radiological assessments, including X-rays and MRI scans, were performed to aid in clinical diagnosis. Routine preoperative investigations were conducted to assess fitness for surgery.

Outcome Measure: The primary outcome measure was based on the change in Harris Hip Score (HHS), which is a comprehensive scoring system encompassing pain, functional activity, range of motion, deformity, and gait of the patient. The scoring domains included pain severity, functional ability, gait quality, and range of motion of the hip joint.

The patients follow up for one year using the Harris Hip Score (HHS)

Technique

With the patient supine on a hip fracture table, approach the hip through a 2 to 3 cm midlateral longitudinal incision centered over the subtrochanteric region using image intensification as a guide, split the fascia lata in the direction of its fibers

Place a 3.2mm threaded guide pin between lateral cortex of the inferior portion of the greater trochanter and the distal portion of the lesser trochanter

Direct the tip of the guide pin to the center of the diseased portion of the bone Overream the guide pins with an 8mm reamer.

Activated PRP which was prepared prior to the surgery was injected via a 10 ml syringe in the drilling track with spinal needle gauge 22 and then the opening is closed by soft tissue plug. Closure of the incisions was done in layers. The patient was instructed to be kept on six weeks off weight bear to avoid collapse.

Post-Operative Protocol: Patients were kept NBM for 6 hours post-operatively. Monitoring of vital was done. Injection Ceftriaxone 1gm IV BD was given till POD -3, followed by Tablet Cefixime 200 mg BD for 7 days. Oral analgesics were given as and when needed. Dressing of the surgical wound was done on the 2nd post-operative day. Patients were discharged on 3rd post-operative day. Patients were recalled on the 12th post-operative day for Suture removal were removed on the 10th or 12th post-operative day, depending upon the condition of the wound. Physiotherapy of the affected limb was started from 1st day post-operatively. Gradual increments in the intensity of physiotherapy were

done. Static and dynamic Quadriceps and hamstring strengthening exercises, pelvic lifting exercises, along with knee and ankle mobilization, were started from 1st day post-operatively or as tolerated by the patient.

Non-weight bearing mobilization with the help of walker/crutches was started from the 2nd post-operative day or as tolerated by the patient.

Results

1. Sex Ratio: Out of 20 patients of early AVN, 15 (75%) were males and 5 (25%) females.

Table 1: Sex Ratio

	Frequency	Percentage
Male	15	75%
Female	5	25%

Graph 1: Sex Ratio

2. Age incidence

Table 2: Age incidence

Age	Frequency	Percentage
<30	3	15%
31-40	11	55%
41-50	5	25%
51-60	1	5%

Graph 2: Age incidence

The mean age of all the patients was 35 years (range 18 to 54 years), with maximum patients from the age group 30 to 40 years (55%)

So out of a total of 26 hips, 18 patients (69.3%) had right-sided AVN, and 8 patients (30.7%) had left-sided AVN.

3. Side Affected: Out of 20 patients, 6 patients (30%) had bilateral AVN.

4. Etiology

Table 3: Causative factor

Causative Factor	Frequency	Percentage
Trauma	4	20%
Alcohol	10	50%
Steroid	5	25%
Sickle cell disease	1	5%

Graph 3: Causative factor

Out of 20 patients, in 16 patients (80%), the causative etiology was non-traumatic, while in 4 patients (20%), it was traumatic. Out of 16 patients with non-traumatic etiology, 1 patient (5%) had sickle cell disease, 5 patients (25%) due to steroid intake, and 10 patients (50%) were chronic alcoholism.

5. Classification

Table 4: Ficat & Arlet Staging

Stage of AVN (Ficat&Arlet)	Number of Cases	Percentage
I	2	7.7%
IIA	16	61.5%
IIB	8	30.8%

Graph 4: Ficat&Arlet Staging

Out of 26 hips, according to the Ficat and Arlet scoring system, 16 hips (61.5%) had grade IIA disease, 8 hips (30.8%) had grade IIB disease, and 2 patients (7.7%) grade I disease.

6. Complications

Table 5: Complications

Complications	Number of cases	Percentage
Infection & Wound dehiscence	3	15%
Restriction of movements	4	20%
Requirement of THR	6	30%

Graph 5: Complications

Out of 20 patients, 3 patients (15%) had superficial infections which healed on subsequently with IV Antibiotics, 4 patients (20%) had restriction of movements and 6 patients (30%) required replacement surgery in follow up period

7. Harris Hip Score among Study Population:

The mean pre-operative Harris Hip Score of our study was 67.4, and the mean post-operative Harris hip score of our study was 86.8. So improvement in the mean Harris Hip score was 19.4.

Table 6: Harris Hip Score

Parameters	Pre-operative	Post-operative
Pain	24.2	39.4
Functional activity	8.8	11.9
Range of motion	5.4	6.05
Final HHS	67.4	86.8

Graph 6; Functional results

8. Functional results

Table 7: Functional results

Functional results	Number of cases	Percentage
Excellent	7	35%
Good	6	30%
Fair	2	10%
Poor	5	25%

The final outcome, on the basis of Harris Hip Score in 7 patients (35%), was excellent, 6 patients (30%)

was good, 2 patients (10%) was fair, and in 5 patients (25%) was poor

9. Out of 20 cases, 8 patients (30%) showed limitation of the progression of the disease, 5 (15%) patients progressed to the further stages of

the disease and 7 patients (55%) had remission of the disease.

Intra-Operative Images

Figure 1:

Radiological Assessment

Figure 2: Pre-operative X ray

Figure 3: 3 months follow up

Figure 4: 9 months follow up

Figure 5: 1 year follow up

Figure 6:

Discussion

Age Distribution

S.No	Series	Mean age
1	Soni et al., 2019	35.5
2	Patel et al., 2015	30.4
3	Current study	35

Sex Distribution

S.No	Series	Male dominance
1	Soni et al., 2019	88%
2	Patel et al., 2015	80%
3	Current study	75%

Etiology

Series	Traumatic	Non traumatic
Soni et al., 2019	40%	60%
Patel et al., 2015	30%	70%
Current study	20%	80%

Classification

Series	Stage I	Stage IIA	Stage IIB
Soni et al., 2019	27%	52%	21%
Patel et al., 2015	16.6%	53.3%	30%
Current study	7.7%	61.5%	30.8%

Harris Hip Score

Series	Per-operative score (Mean)	Post-operative score (Mean)
Soni et al., 2019	73.1	83.2
Patel et al., 2015	61.81	79.73
Current study	67.4	86.8

We have compared our study with (Soni et al., 2019), in which 25 patients of early AVN were treated with core decompression and PRP

infiltration and with (Patel et al., 2015) in which 39 patients with of early AVN were treated with core decompression and PRP infiltration.

1. Age-The mean age of our study was 33.4years when compared to
2. 35.5 years in Soni et al. and 30.4 years in (Patel et al., 2015) [6]
3. Gender - 75% of cases in our study were males and 25% females when compared to 88% males and 12% females in (Soni et al., 2019)7 and 80%
4. Site of affection - In our study, 20% of patients had bilateral affection, when compared to 52% of Soni et al. (2019) and 46% of (Patel et al., 2015)
5. Etiology-In our study,80%of patients had non-traumatic etiology while 20% had traumatic as compared to 60% non-traumatic and 40% traumatic in (Soni et al., 2019)
6. Staging - In our study, 62.5% of hips had grade IIA disease, 20.83% had grade IIB disease and 16.667% grade I disease. In (Soni et al., 2019), there were 73% with grade II and 27% with grade I disease. In (Patel et al., 2015), there were 53.33% grade IIA, 30% grade IIB and 16.66% grade I.
7. Harris Hip Score [8] - The mean pre-operative Harris Hip Score of our study was 64.3, and the mean post-operative Harris hip score of our study was 80.2. In (Soni et al., 2019), it was 73.1 pre-operative and 83.2 post-operative, while in (Patel et al., 2015), it was 61.81 pre-operative and 79.73 post-operative.
8. Outcome - Final outcome in our study was, on the basis of Harris Hip Score in 5 patients (25%) was excellent, 7 patients (35%) was good, 5 patients (25%) was fair, and in 3 patients (15%) was poor. In 10.5% cases.

References

1. Arbab D, König DP. Atraumatic femoral head necrosis in adults: epidemiology, etiology, diagnosis and treatment. *Dtsch Arztebl Int.* 2016; 113(3):31-8.
2. Khanuja, H. S., Mont, M. A., Etienne, G., Hungerford, D. S. 2001. Treatment Algorithm for Osteonecrosis of the Hip. *Techniques in Orthopaedics*, 16(1):80– 89.
3. Ficat RP. Idiopathic bone necrosis of the femoral head: early diagnosis and treatment. *J Bone Joint SurgBr.* 1985; 67:3-9.
4. Fairbank, A. C., Bhatia, D., Jinnah, R. H., Hungerford, D. S. 1995. Long-term results of core decompression for ischaemic necrosis of the femoral head. *The Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery. British volume*, 77-B (1):42–49.
5. Shrivastava, S., Singh, P. K., Taywade, S. 2016. Sandeep's technique for assisted regeneration of skin. *STARS therapy*, 4. 6. Patel, P. S., Agarwal, T., Sooknundun, M., Mohapatra, A. R., Joshi, H. S., Salgia, A. 2015. Management of stage I and II A/B avascular necrosis of femoral head with core decompression autologous cancellous bone grafting and platelet rich plasma factors. *Medical Journal of Dr. D.Y. Patil University*, 8(6):713.
6. Soni, S. K., Chouhan, V. S., Joshi, V. 2019. Study of functional outcome of core decompression with platelet-rich plasma enhanced cancellous bone graft in avascular necrosis of femoral head grade I and II. *International Journal of Orthopaedics*, 5(2):710–713.
7. Söderman, P., Malchau, H. 1976. Is the Harris hip score system useful to study the outcome of total hip replacement? *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research*, 384:189–197.